

the product and that of the authentic fluorenone were identical in all respect, ν_{\max} (nujol), 1 950, 1 925, 1 830, 1 715, 1 610, 1 595, 1 445, 1 370, 1 295, 1 195, 1 095, 1 080, 950, 915, 880, 810, 780, 730, 665 and 645 cm^{-1} .

Oxidation of mandelic acid: A mixture of mandelic acid (1.5 g), ammonium metavanadate (2.4 g), perchloric acid (20 ml) and water (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 10 min. The deep blue reaction mixture was cooled and extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene (1 : 1, v/v; 3 \times 50 ml). The organic layer was extracted with sodium hydroxide solution (1 N; 20 ml; preserved), washed with water (2 \times 25 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvents an oily residue (trace) was obtained which furnished the 2,4-DNP derivative of benzaldehyde, m.p. 235–37°. It corresponded to 15% formation of benzaldehyde in the reaction.

The aforementioned alkaline extract was acidified (congo red) with concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether (3 \times 25 ml). The organic layer was washed with a little water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue (0.5 g), obtained after removal of the solvent, was crystallised from water to furnish benzoic acid (0.4 g), m.p. 121°, m.m.p. with authentic benzoic acid remained undepressed.

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Isomerisation of Double Bond in Nitrosteroids

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MITIU¹ and Jones² reported the conversion of 6-nitro-5-ene to the corresponding 6 β -nitro-4-ene in the cholestane series by using methanolic solution of KOH in 6 days. In this paper we want to report a quick, convenient and versatile method for the transformation of readily available 6-nitrocholest-5-enes (1–4) to 6 β -nitrocholest-4-enes (5–7) in excellent yield.

- 1, R=H
- 2, R=Cl
- 3, R=OAc
- 4, R=OH

- 5, R=H
- 6, R=OCH₃
- 7, R=OH
- 8, R=OAc

6-Nitrocholest-5-ene (1)³ and its 3 β -chloro (2)⁴, 3 β -acetoxy (3)⁵ and 3 β -hydroxy (4)⁶ analogues in acetonitrile when treated with methanolic 5% KOH afforded 6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (5), 3 β -methoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (6) and 3 β -hydroxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (7), respectively. Further acetylation of 7 gave 3 β -acetoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (8). These nitrosteroids have been characterised on the basis of their spectral data and chemical transformation.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were determined with a Perkin–Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were run on a Varian A60 instrument with Me₄Si as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel. An aqueous 20% solution of perchloric acid was used as the spraying agent. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

General procedure: The nitroolefin (1; 1.0 g) was dissolved in acetonitrile (25 ml) and methanolic 5% KOH (15 ml) was added. The content was refluxed for 2 h on a water-bath. After completion of reaction, the solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and again with water. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The semisolid mass thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol to give 6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (5; 0.82 g, 82%), m.p. and m.m.p. 112° (lit⁷. 113–15°) (Found: C,

78.1; H, 10.9; N, 3.5. $C_{27}H_{45}NO_3$ requires: C, 78.0; H, 10.8; N, 3.4%; ν_{max} 1545, 1465 and 1375 cm^{-1} (non-conjugated NO_2); δ 5.88 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.56 (dd, J_{ae} 4, J_{ee} 2 Hz, C6- α H), 1.16 (C10- CH_3), 0.7 (C13- CH_3), 0.9 and 0.87 (other methyl protons).

Under similar reaction conditions (same amounts of reactants were used in each case) the nitroolefins (2-4) provided 3 β -methoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (6; 0.80 g, 80%), m.p. 116° (Found: C, 75.6; H, 10.6; N, 3.1. $C_{28}H_{47}NO_3$ requires: C, 75.5; H, 10.57; N, 3.14%); (negative Beilstein test); ν_{max} 1545, 1470 and 1375 (non-conjugated NO_2) and 1080 cm^{-1} (OCH_3); δ 5.96 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.63 (dd, J_{ae} 5, J_{ee} 2.5 Hz, C6- α H), 5.13 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 3.32 (s, OCH_3), 1.2 (C10- CH_3), 0.7 (C13- CH_3), 0.93 and 0.83 (other methyl protons) and 3 β -hydroxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (7; 0.86 g, 86%), m.p. and m.m.p. 154° (lit.⁹ 154.5-155°) (Found: C, 75.2; H, 10.4; N, 3.4. $C_{27}H_{46}NO_3$ requires: C, 75.1; H, 10.3; N, 3.2%); ν_{max} 3450 (OH), 1540, 1350 and 1375 cm^{-1} (non-conjugated NO_2); δ 5.85 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.63 (dd, J_{ae} 4, J_{ee} 2 Hz, C6- α H), 4.12 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 1.2 (C10- CH_3), 0.73 (C13- CH_3), 0.93 and 0.83 (other methyl protons).

Acetylation of 7: 3 β -Hydroxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (7; 100 mg) was treated with purified pyridine (1 ml) and freshly distilled acetic anhydride (0.8 ml) and warmed on a water-bath for 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured into water and solid thus obtained was air-dried. Recrystallisation of solid from acetone gave 3 β -acetoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (8; 0.72 g, 72%), m.p. and m.m.p. 101° (lit.⁹ 101-102°) (Found: C, 73.7; H, 10.1; N, 3.0. $C_{29}H_{47}NO_3$ requires: C, 73.6; H, 9.9; N, 2.9%); ν_{max} 1730 (CH_3COO), 1545, 1465 and 1375 cm^{-1} (non-conjugated NO_2); δ 5.75 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.58 (dd, J_{ae} 4, J_{ee} 2 Hz, C6- α H), 2.0 (s, C3- β -O- $COCH_3$), 1.18 (C10- CH_3), 0.70 (C13- CH_3), 0.90 and 0.79 (other methyl protons).

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Synthesis of some New Carboxanilides and Amides of 8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxylic Acid as Possible Antifungal and Antibacterial Agents

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COUMARIN derivatives are known to have antifungal and antibacterial properties¹⁻³. On the other hand, haloacetamides^{4,5} possess amoebicidal activity and substituted-acetamides^{6,7} have local anaesthetic property. With a view to prepare better therapeutically active compound the present work is undertaken.

The present paper deals with the synthesis of some anilides and amides by reaction of 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxylic acid⁸ (1) via acid chloride with aliphatic, alicyclic, aromatic and heterocyclic primary and secondary amines. The structures of the compounds were assigned on the basis of their satisfactory elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectra.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Microanalysis of compounds were performed on a Coleman instrument, ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard.

8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxanilides and amides: The acid chloride was prepared by refluxing 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (2 g) with thionyl chloride (4 ml) and dry benzene (50 ml) until the solution was clear (3 h). The excess thionyl chloride and benzene were distilled off. To the acid chloride in dry ether (60 ml), two mole equivalent of the amine was added. The mixture was then stirred for 3 h, cooled and filtered. The solid product was dried and washed with water. The product was crystallised from the proper solvent. The physical data of compounds 2 and 3 are presented in Tables 1 and 2.